

Capital contradictions in the age of incorporation: Queer and trans materialism at work

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the contradictions at the heart of neoliberal capitalism create new modes of inclusion and exclusion: inclusion of some LGBT citizen-consumers, and exclusion of queer and trans others.

Amber Hollibaugh & Margot Weiss

we must ask how we might make less violent use of one another.

Trish Salah

“LGBTQI2S¹ people in Canada continue to face discrimination and exclusion in the workforce,” asserts Egale, an advocacy group founded in Ottawa in 1986 that today describes itself as “Canada’s leading organization” for queer and trans people. In a report on ‘Workplace Inclusion,’ Egale argues that, although, “[o]n a global scale, Canada is considered a progressive champion in employment supports for LGBTQI2S people,” there is considerable evidence of “persistent issues for LGBTQI2S people in the workplace” (Egale, 2020). These “persistent issues” include barriers to hiring, wage penalties, harassment and discrimination, and disproportionate rates of unemployment and underemployment; all experienced most acutely by those people under the ‘queer’ umbrella who are trans, gender non-conforming, Black, Indigenous and/or racialized. Further, the report notes, alongside and related to these labour market challenges, a disproportionate number of LGBTQI2S people face poor health outcomes, housing precarity and higher than average poverty rates.

To substantiate these claims, Egale surveys not only research conducted in Canada (eg. Fosbrook et al, 2020; Ng and Rumens, 2017; Waite et al, 2019). It also draws on US and UK scholarship and policy documents, and on literature reviews that convey findings from a variety of national contexts where neoliberalism and LGBTQ+ legislative ‘equalities’ coincide (eg. Beauregard et al, 2018; Calvard et al, 2019; Denier and Waite, 2019; Webster et al., 2018). It picks up on the insights of literatures on LGBTQ+ work, workers, and workplace experiences that have blossomed in fields such as administrative and organizational

studies, sociology, social work, and psychology since the 1980s (see Anteby and Anderson, 2014; Barnard et al, 2022; Colgan and Rumens, 2015; DeSouza et al, 2017; Maji et al, 2024; McFadden, 2015). Based on copious research, it is now well established within a number of disciplinary and cross-disciplinary literatures that sexual orientation and gender identity matter in the workplace, that labour market practices and outcomes are extremely consequential in the lives and livelihoods of LGBTQ+ people, and that legal gains (where they exist) have not eliminated marginalization and exclusion for queer and trans people at work or beyond.

In response to these discouraging truths, Egale echoes the common diagnoses and prescriptions offered in the dominant strains of LGBTQ+ work scholarship. It argues that poor labour market outcomes for queer and trans people evidence the persistence of heteronormativity, cis-normativity, homophobia and transphobia at work, and that these ills result from “the failure of organizations to protect LGBTQI2S employees and the failure of Canada’s current workplace and human rights frameworks.” Further, and again echoing much scholarly literature, Egale states that these are social/cultural and policy implementation problems and that, as such, queer and trans inequities and exclusions can be overcome by maintaining a “safe working environment” and “ensuring that internal workplace processes and supports are inclusive of the needs of diverse LGBTQI2S people.” What we need, in this widely influential formulation, is more and better “social infrastructure” in the form of equity-oriented education and training programs for employers and employees that will facilitate “cultural and societal shifts toward LGBTQI2S equality across the country” (Egale, 2020).

In this paper, we aim to contribute to the scholarly literatures and related policy debates on LGBTQ+ work and life that Egale highlights, and to bring these debates into economic geography and queer and trans geographies, fields which have heretofore only minimally examined

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¹ The acronym LGBTQI2S that Egale uses throughout its report stands for “Lesbian Gay Bisexual Transgender Queer Intersex 2 Spirit.” As no single acronym can capture all possible permutations of sexual orientations and gender identities, in this paper we choose to use “LGBTQ+” and “queer and trans” as stand-ins for a broad range of sexual orientation and gender identity designators.

sexual orientation and gender identity and/in the workplace (see: Cockayne, 2024; Lewis and Mills, 2016). We conducted a two year study of LGBTQ+ workers in Sudbury and Windsor, mid-size cities in the Canadian province of Ontario. In 2018 and 2019, in conjunction with several other academics, staff from the national unions Unifor and United Steelworkers and the Sudbury Workers Education and Advocacy Centre and Windsor Workers Education Centre, and aided by a community advisory board, we researched the labour market outcomes and workplace experiences of LGBTQ+ people through a survey which yielded 673 total responses (405 from respondents in Sudbury and 266 from respondents in Windsor), and 50 in-depth interviews (26 from respondents in Sudbury and 24 from respondents in Windsor).²

Our empirical results (described in brief below, and more fully in Mills, 2020; Mills and Oswin, 2024; Mills and Owens, 2023; Owens et al, 2022) are in line with the broad findings of the existing literature as presented by Egale. We thus share concerns about widespread queer and trans precarity and its ties to employment, and find it heartening that the experiences of LGBTQ+ people in the workplace are taken seriously by many scholars, mainstream organizers, and employers in Canada and elsewhere. Here though, we argue against the now widespread conventional policy and scholarly wisdom that employment-related LGBTQ+ precarities (as experienced in Sudbury, Windsor and countless other locales) can be overcome with education about LGBTQ+ issues in the workplace and better implementation of rights provisions alone, and we advocate for other ways of knowing and articulating the problematic of LGBTQ+ work. That is, we argue against the predominant ‘queer liberalism’ of dominant strains of LGBTQ+ work scholarship, and for a grappling with the fact that, as gay historian John D’Emilio long ago observed and large bodies of queer and trans Marxist and materialist literatures have enforced since, “in the most profound sense, [cisheteropatriarchal racial] capitalism is the problem” (1983, p. 110). Relatedly, we argue for the utility, within and beyond the discipline of geography, of the analytic lenses of ‘homonormativity’ and ‘homonationalism’ for understanding the structuring of queer and trans life (including but not limited to work and employment outcomes) in countries like Canada.

In what follows, informed by and in conversation with scholarship on queer and trans Marxism and materialism, we draw on the experiences of our respondents across the three dominant sectors of the neoliberal economies in which they live (the public sector, low wage services, and manufacturing and resource processing) to emphasize the fact that while persistent homophobia and transphobia shape the lives of queer and trans people within and beyond the workplace in Sudbury and Windsor, so do liberal structuring logics that facilitate assimilation into or tolerance within inequitable systems for some while preventing transformative change for all. Thus, while considerable existing scholarship on LGBTQ+ work points out the uneven inclusion of queer and trans people within workplaces and tends to advocate for more and better inclusion as the best remedy to broad-based precarities and harms, we join critical queer and trans scholars who see homonormativity and homonationalism not as individual attributes but as dominant structural logics and who highlight inclusion as not a benign individual byproduct

² Multiple participant recruitment strategies were utilized in order to minimize sampling bias: union membership email lists; postcards at cafes and community organizations; making surveys available on iPads and as paper copies at local Pride events; promoting the study on local radio stations; and placing ads on Facebook, Instagram, and the geosocial meet-up platforms Grindr and Scruff. Community advisory committees in each city helped with survey distribution, and we encouraged participants to distribute the survey to members of their social network with a prize incentive. Participants in the study identified as LGBTQ+, were at least sixteen years old, and had worked in Sudbury or Windsor in the past year; and our sample was broad-based in terms of age, gender, sexual orientation, gender identity, race, and Indigeneity (for a full breakdown of the demographic characteristics of participants in the study, see Mills et al, 2020).

of rights within recognition frameworks but as a form of structural harm and an indicator of the need for systems change. Highlighting the ways in which the capitalist good jobs/bad jobs dichotomy connects to the LGBTQ+ age of equalities – ie. the ways in which individual freedoms and access within the workplace for some LGBTQ+ people systemically depend upon forms of continued structural dispossession – we amplify calls for queer and trans anti-capitalist responses to the contradictions that are evident in LGBTQ+ workplace and labour market experiences under neoliberal multiculturalism.

1. Recognizing cisheteropatriarchal racial capitalism

It is not surprising that Egale, in its 2020 report or in its extensive workplace education and training work, does not frame the plight of LGBTQ+ workers as related to capitalism. There is a long history of left, internationalist queer and trans activism that challenges ‘straight’ society and its corporatist, carceral underpinnings. Indeed, Stonewall was a riot led by gender non-conforming/trans of colour street activists like Marsha P. Johnson and Sylvia Rivera. But while these towering figures are posthumously hailed as progenitors of a global contemporary LGBTQ+ movement, they faced opprobrium and rejection from middle class white queers in their lifetimes. Further, while Johnson and Rivera fought in their organizing and activism with Street Transvestite Action Revolutionaries (STAR) for a different world of jobs, welfare, housing, freedom, and dignity for all, these radical objectives have been cast aside by an establishment LGBTQ+ movement that pursues access and assimilation to bourgeois life and institutions for some (Gill-Peterson, 2024; Stanley, 2021). The US version of this story is widely told, but it has parallels elsewhere, and Egale is an example of a Canadian human rights and advocacy organization that has maintained a liberal rather than progressive/radical bent since its inception (see Kinsman, 2024; McCaskell, 2016). It is also not surprising that a critique of capitalism is not prominent within LGBTQ+ work scholarship. This literature has emerged largely in the fields of administrative and organizational studies, fields operating generally as handmaidens to the economy. There is a sizeable literature in social work and psychology too, but these are helping professions that tend to be focused on finding manageable solutions to people’s daily ills while often working in service of corporate and state goals to produce a ‘healthy’ and ‘productive’ populace. And none of these fields are ones in which radical queer and trans theory and scholarship have been historically deeply entrenched.

To be clear, we do not make these broad observations to malign efforts to understand and address the workings of homophobia and transphobia in the workplace within these specific advocacy and scholarly circles. Such efforts certainly have tangible material effects for many. But, they also, even if often unwittingly, have the adverse outcome of narrowing our field of vision in ways that limit understanding and response. As Petrus Liu pointedly states in the concluding lines of ‘Queer Theory and the Specter of Marxism,’ an article published in the same year as Egale’s report:

Seeing the LGBTQIA+ ‘issue’ as a battle against discriminatory attitudes and patterns of evaluation, critics believe that the proper remedy is the promotion of ‘diversity and inclusion’ in the workplace or education. What the language of diversity and inclusion leaves out, of course, is the critique and analysis of the historical processes that authorized certain individuals to decide whom to include, tolerate, and accept in the first place. The implicit message to queer and other oppressed people is that, instead of questioning and demanding fundamental changes in the existing relations of power, they can rely on the good will of enlightened individuals in positions of power to bring about social change (2020, p. 42).

He continues: “A materialist methodology is a timely response at this critical juncture to counter the liberal-pluralist ideology that gender and sexual minorities only suffer from prejudices or invisibility” (2020, p. 42). And there exists a wealth of thought, spanning decades, on the ways

in which the geographically-infllected experiences of queer and trans people, the global logics and systems of heteronormativity and cisnormativity, and the likewise global realities of political homophobia and transphobia are intimately produced by and inextricably bound up with capitalism (for overviews of these literatures, in addition to Liu, see: [Jaleel and Savcı, 2023](#); [Terán and Travis, 2024](#)). Further, much of this scholarship grapples with the ways in which capitalism is constitutively produced with and by systems of racial domination, colonialism and patriarchy ([hooks, 1984](#)) and that ‘capitalism’ is therefore most productively deployed (and indeed we deploy it as such in this article) as a shorthand for ‘cisheteropatriarchal racial capitalism’ ([Alexander, 1994](#); [Cohen, 1997](#); [Hong and Ferguson, 2011](#)).

As mentioned above, though, while there is an extensive history of well-articulated queer and trans theoretical critiques of capitalism and of queer and trans anti-capitalist activist engagements, the ascendance over the last several decades of a ‘queer liberalism’ that prioritizes rights and recognition and largely ignores issues of economic justice is a strong counter-force. And, as David Eng, Jack Halberstam, and José Muñoz pointed out two decades ago: “the turning away from a sustained examination of the vast inequalities in civil society and commercial life that mark the paradoxes of queer liberalism find an unwitting accomplice in certain strands of contemporary queer studies” that fail to recognize that “the problems of political economy cannot be abstracted away from the racial, gendered, and sexual hierarchies of the nation-state but must in fact be understood as operating in and through them” (2005, p. 11; see also [Eng, 2010](#)). Such moves to ‘abstract away’ political economy from processes of social structuration and differentiation, both within and beyond the academy in the US (which much of the literature discussed in the last few paragraphs emanates from and is concerned with) as well as in places like Canada, are no accident. Rather, following Jodi Melamed, this political and economic delinking is encouraged within and conditioned by neoliberal multiculturalism, “a central ideology and mode of social organization that seeks to manage racial [and other, interconnected] contradictions on a national and international scale” (2006, p. 3; also see [Ferguson, 2012](#) on global capital and the incorporation of difference within the academy). Under this formulation, modes of difference are incorporated for capitalist and state-based ends as “new categories of privilege and stigma determined by ideological, economic, and cultural criteria overlay older, conventional racial [and other, interconnected] categories” (p. 2) in ways that prop up liberal fantasies of inclusion while hindering “thinking about or acting against the biopolitics of global capitalism” (p. 3). And, in cognate analyses to Melamed’s, Lisa [Duggan \(2002\)](#) and Jasbir [Puar \(2007\)](#) – both central thinkers within queer and trans Marxist and materialist theoretical trajectories, though rarely described that way, as [Liu \(2020\)](#) points out – give us influential tools to use in grappling with neoliberal multiculturalism’s selective LGBTQ+ inclusions with their conceptualizations of ‘homonormativity’ and ‘homonationalism.’

Homonormativity, following Duggan, describes “the sexual politics of neoliberalism,” a “politics that does not contest dominant heteronormative assumptions and institutions, but upholds and sustains them, while promising the possibility of a demobilized gay constituency and a privatized, depoliticized gay culture anchored in domesticity and consumption” (2002, p. 179). Homonationalism, in Puar’s terms, relates to a “brand of homosexuality [that] operates as a regulatory script not only of normative gayness, queerness, or homosexuality, but also of the racial and national norms that reinforce these sexual subjects” (2007, p. 2); a regulatory script which renders “some homosexual subjects...complicit with heterosexual nationalist formations rather than inherently or automatically excluded from or opposed to them” (p. 4). It is worth noting here that, as Kath [Browne et al \(2021\)](#), p. 1322) note in the flagship journal *Progress in Human Geography*, “geographers have criticized the concept of homonormativity extensively.” Most notably, Gavin Brown writes in strong rebuke that has been widely taken up that homonormativity is “a metropolitan concept that denigrates ‘ordinary’ gay lives.” He argues that it, “has increasingly come to be represented in

both academic and activist writing as a homogeneous, global eternal entity that exists outside all of us and exerts its terrifying, normative power on gay lives everywhere” (2012, p. 1066), and that “most gay people do not live in the metropolitan centers where homonormativity has been described, theorized and critiqued (and even many of those who do live in those locations do not live immersed in the spaces and social relations that have come to be described as homonormative)” (2012, p. 1068). And these critiques have, within geography, come to be applied to the notion of homonationalism as well. Here, we respectfully dispute this characterization. On our reading, which resonates with scholarship within and beyond our discipline (eg. [Bhagat \(2018\)](#); [Catungal et al \(2021\)](#); [Goh \(2018\)](#); [Manalansan \(2005\)](#); [Morgensen \(2012\)](#); [Muñoz \(2016\)](#); [Roberts and Catungal \(2018\)](#); [Rao \(2015\)](#); [Rosenberg \(2017, 2021\)](#); and, [Rouhani \(2017\)](#)), neither Duggan nor Puar put forward homonormativity and homonationalism as descriptors of individual attributes or identity markers, or as accusations meant to delineate ‘good’ from ‘bad’ queer and trans people or places. Rather than denoting new social or spatial categories, these concepts highlight shifting conditions for subject formation and political action under neoliberal multiculturalism whereby state, capitalism, sexuality, and gender identity relationships are reoriented, and the liberal thought which runs through Egale and much of the LGBTQ+ work literature gains traction.³ Duggan, Puar and many others highlight the selective incorporation of LGBTQ+ populations into state and capitalist institutions that this reorientation has allowed, and attend to the splitting and splintering of queer and trans politics, movements and scholarship that it has produced.

Homonormativity and homonationalism, though concepts developed in relation to mostly US-related phenomena and geographies, have been taken up extensively by scholars and activists in a wide range of places given the transnational and globalized realities of queer and trans lives, livelihoods, and politics. “Homonationalism is not a state practice per se,” Puar clarifies. “It is instead the historical convergence of state practices, transnational circuits of queer commodity culture and human rights paradigms, and broader global phenomena such as the increasing entrenchment of Islamophobia” (2013, p. 337). The same can be said of homonormativity. In other words, both concepts describe not some sort of overarching and coherent national or global force. Instead, they diagnose partial, fragmentary, demographically and geographically uneven, and constantly changing power relations under neoliberalism/late capitalism. They point to the ways in which fractures within queer and trans communities and movements along lines of race, class, gender, nationality, age, and ability, for instance, are not solely the products of individual biases and misinformation. They are also, and fundamentally, produced by cisheteropatriarchal racial capitalist formations as such formations adapt and change, regulate and re-regulate, territorialize and reterritorialize, always in ways that maximize profit and efficiency by parsing the ‘productive’ from the ‘unproductive’, the ‘worthy’ from the ‘unworthy.’ So, while homonormativity and homonationalism, in Duggan and Puar’s terms, are not projects of praise or admonishment of particular ‘good’ and ‘bad’ subjects and spaces, these conceptualizations have shone a spotlight on the ways in which states and capital do indeed make such distinctions, to profound material effect. Among the ramifications of the reality that some queer and (far fewer) trans people in some places are “recruited for the sustenance of the late-colonial, capitalist, modernist nation-state” ([Walcott, 2015](#), p. viii): coalitions of the disenfranchised stretch and break, fracturing queer and trans communities from within and undercutting activism against broad interlinked processes of normalization, regulation, and exploitation; privilege is consolidated; so too are marginalization and deprivation; and we end up, as Liu (cited above) notes, with an off the mark conventional wisdom

³ [Duggan \(2002\)](#) and [Puar \(2007\)](#) focus on lesbian and gay politics and movements. For examples of analyses of trans normativities, see: [Aizura \(2018\)](#); [Spade \(2011\)](#).

that a 'diversity and inclusion' approach in arenas like the worlds of work and education will cure queer and trans ills.

Working against the tide of "[l]iberal ideology [that] longs to veil the violence of capitalism from view" (Rosenberg and Villarejo, 2011, p. 3), Duggan and Puar (and many others) thus denounce the rise of a non-redistributive identity politics that fosters ignorance of how modes of late capitalist LGBTQ+ incorporation facilitate the reorganization, rather than undoing, of exploitation and inequality. Neoliberalism since the 1970s has wrought rampant global privatization, assetization and financialization of education, healthcare, housing, land and natural resources, the gutting of welfare provisions, obscene intensifications of wealth and extensifications of poverty, the sharpening of carceral and border logics and practices, and catastrophic environmental decline. As Meg Wesling observes, "the performance of gender and sexuality constitutes a form of labor, accruing both material and affective value" (2011, p. 108; see also: David, 2017; Irving, 2008) in all of this, as "the embrace of queer spectacle and gay and lesbian rights has become a suspicious marker of the state's own investment in a display of modernization" (123). Canada is a state that participates in this sort of performance and, as OmiSoore Dryden and Suzanne Lenon, in the introduction to their important 2015 edited collection *Disrupting Queer Inclusion: Canadian Homonationalisms and the Politics of Belonging*, observe: "the 'turn to life' for some lesbian-gay-queer subjects (i.e., their enrollment within legal, cultural and consumer arenas) is now possible because of [for instance] the simultaneous curtailing of welfare provisions and immigrant rights, as well as the expansion of state powers to conduct surveillance and to (indefinitely) detain and deport" (p. 6). The collection's authors, "insist on the continual interrogation of the associated complicities, collusions, and costs of inclusion in order to unsettle it as a signifier for liberation and justice – that is, to disturb and unsettle the idea(l) and dreams of 'inclusion' itself" (p. 16).

The 'costs of inclusion' are explored in the Dryden and Lenon (2015) collection in relation to a number of topics that are also well covered in the broad homonormativity and homonationalism literatures, including: refugee claims, citizenship policies, marriage laws, the military, sporting mega-events, Pride marches, hate crime statutes, and urban politics. Workplace inclusion is absent from the book's discussions (one edited volume cannot cover everything!), but it is certainly a terrain within which homonormative and homonationalist dynamics play out. For instance, in an early analysis of 'queer precarity,' Amber Hollibaugh and Margot Weiss point out that: "Because of histories of discrimination and criminalization, many queer and trans people are funneled into low-wage jobs, or seek them out as sites where gender expression and sexuality will not be disciplined in the same ways as in professional jobs" (2015, p. 19). On this basis, they take issue with the facts that "even when labor organizing takes up these issues, it tends to focus on inclusion or identity politics" and that the US mainstream LGBT movement focuses on marriage equality and perpetuates a 'myth of gay affluence' while "leaving aside any analysis of class or economic inequality or poverty – much less an analysis of capitalism" (2015, p. 19). Trish Salah examines queer and trans organizing within the Canadian labour movement, noting that: "in the increasing homonormativity of gay and lesbian rights activism, both outside and within the union movement, there was a prioritizing of the fight for 'equal marriage' over virtually all other GLBT issues" (2022, p. 250). She demonstrates that the concerns of trans workers and, particularly, of trans sex workers – whom she describes as "demonstrably some of the most courageous, hard-working, and effective advocates for trans people in the country" (p. 250) – were cast aside due to "the pitfalls of a narrow identity politics, as well as sex work stigma, and arguably a failure of labour analysis" (p. 249–50; also see Berg, 2021).

Zooming out to the global scale, Rahul Rao (2015) counters the 'business case' for LGBTQ+ rights – i.e. the argument made within some LGBTQ+ policy circles and, indeed, within the LGBTQ+ work literature – that discrimination hampers productivity and that rooting out homophobia is thus good for the bottom line. Coining the term

'homocapitalism', he argues that, in relation to "activist stances against homophobia" by "leading institutions of global capitalism" like the World Bank and the International Monetary Fund, "we must ask not only what the Bank is doing for queers but also what queers are doing for the Bank" (p. 38) as "a radical agenda is effectively conscripted in the service of the capitalist imperative of expanding output, productivity and markets" (p. 41; also see: Bedford, 2009; Gosine, 2010). Finally, at the level of the workplace, in a study of call center workers in the Philippines, Emmanuel David identifies what he calls the "purple collar" to highlight the fact that, "as transgender people become more integrated across labor markets, their employment as transgender subjects creates the conditions for new kinds of workplace inequalities" (2015, p. 170). And in a study of queer women's experiences in the rural US, Carly Thomsen pushes back against calls by mainstream LGBTQ organizations to 'come out' at work for the cause of LGBTQ equality. She finds that this sort of visibility politics disproportionately benefits employers rather than workers as making a workplace 'gay friendly' is, "a small price to pay for the increased surplus value that companies can extract from trusting, pliant employees" (2021, p. 156). She continues: "That gay rights activists champion such companies because they ostensibly do not fire their employees for displaying their 'true selves' at work should concern all of us. How low our bar has become" (2021, p. 157).

All of these observations – that queer and trans people tend to be funneled into low wage jobs, that the labour issues facing LGBTQ+ people are equally as pressing as rights and recognition struggles, that gay-friendliness predominantly fosters productivity and profit to the benefit of employers rather than employees – are relevant to the findings of our study in Sudbury and Windsor. We now turn to those locales, to add to the mountain of evidence that the issues that LGBTQ+ people face at work and in labour markets is far from just a social/cultural phenomenon that can be addressed with equity-based training and better enforcement of rights protections alone.

2. Tales from two deindustrializing cities

Sudbury, located in the northern part of the Canadian province of Ontario, has a population of 179 965 (Clarke, 2024). Windsor, located in southwestern Ontario, has a population of 324 200 (Waddell, 2024). Both are settler colonial cities – Sudbury is in Robinson Huron treaty territory, on ancestral homeland of the Atikameksheng Anishnawbek, while Windsor is the historical meeting place for the Three Fires Confederacy of First Nations, comprised of the Ojibway, the Odawa, and the Potawatomie – founded in the mid- to late-1800s with economies historically dominated by the mining and automotive manufacturing sectors, respectively. Downsizing, outsourcing, and technological intensification since the 1970s has steadily lessened employment in these sectors in Sudbury and Windsor, however, while knowledge-intensive and service sector employment has expanded in both sites over time (Rutherford and Holmes, 2014; King, 2019; Vinodrai, 2020). Today, while there is still much blue collar work, these cities' labour markets now also consist of a good proportion of public sector and low-wage service sector work. Sudbury and Windsor are thus cities in transition, as neoliberal deindustrialization has – as it tends to do – led to rising unemployment, a shift toward less stable jobs, and income polarization in both places (see Mills and Oswin, 2024). Coincident with these deindustrializing economic trends, both cities are also touched by political trends toward the official valorization of diversity within Canadian urban economies and, in particular, toward increasing social acceptance for LGBTQ+ people in concert with provincial and federal roll-outs of human rights protections on the basis of gender identity and sexual orientation (on the latter, see: Trembley, 2016). While neither Sudbury nor Windsor are especially well-known as LGBTQ+ cultural destinations, both have sizeable LGBTQ+ populations, as well as visible queer and trans night-life and social services, and annual Pride celebrations.

Embarking on research into the labour market and workplace

experiences of LGBTQ+ people in Sudbury and Windsor, we sought to address the facts that most existing research on these topics focuses on individual workplaces or economic sectors, few quantitative studies have explored LGBTQ+ employment experiences in Canada, and related qualitative research has focused on large metropolitan areas to the relative exclusion of smaller cities and resource and manufacturing based regions. The partiality of queer and trans scholarly emphasis on a handful of major cities has been well-critiqued, not least because major metropolitan centres are not in fact the “typical urban home” for LGBTQ+ people (Forstie, 2020). As Gavin Brown importantly argues: “In a period when the hegemonic sexual identities that have held sway for the last 40 years are being redefined in legal statutes, social policy and everyday life...sexual geographers need to reconnect with debates in urban geography and consider the spatial organisation of sexualities across the whole of urban space” (2008, p. 1224–25). In line with Brown, our study sought to explore LGBTQ+ lives in ‘ordinary’ spaces in ‘ordinary’ cities.

As noted above, our overall findings are in line with those summarized by Egale in their 2020 report. On the positive side: 73.3 % of our survey respondents reported that their employer was either somewhat or very supportive of LGBTQ+ people; approximately half of our respondents were in permanent full-time positions; many respondents reported finding community amongst co-workers; and 89.6 % of unionized respondents felt somewhat or fully supported by their unions. On the negative side: 70.5 % of workers reported experiencing some type of harassment or discrimination in their current job (such as avoidance or eye-rolling, verbal harassment and bullying, disrespect for preferred pronouns, and, in a few extreme cases, physical violence); 13.5 % of survey respondents reported having experienced discrimination based on sexual orientation or gender identity as a barrier to finding work; 36.4 % of respondents reported income of less than \$20 000 per year (a slightly higher percentage than the general low income population in each of Sudbury and Windsor); respondents were slightly less likely to be working in well-paid jobs in mining and/or manufacturing than the general population, slightly more likely to be working in the low-wage service sector and/or the public sector; many experienced housing precarity; and poor mental health was overwhelmingly reported by those who did not feel supported at work and/or who had low incomes. Further, in breaking down all responses, trans, gender non-conforming, and Black, Indigenous and/or racialized respondents, as well as – we add to Egale’s list – respondents with health issues and disabilities, fared significantly worse than white/cisgendered respondents overall.

Thus, workplace inclusion has wrought contradictory outcomes for LGBTQ+ people in Sudbury and Windsor, as it has in many other locales – acceptance and discrimination, security and insecurity, fulfilment and alienation, abundance and scarcity. We now turn to some of the stories of six of our respondents – two from each of the dominant sectors of the cities’ economies, the public sector, low wage services, and manufacturing and resource processing work⁴ – to illustrate specific ways in which their workplace and labour market experiences are inflected by enduring forms of dispossession and exclusion as well as by new modes of entitlement and inclusion. In these narratives, there is plenty of evidence of a changed work/labour market landscape for LGBTQ+ people, despite the persistence of instances of intolerance and discrimination. There is also plenty of evidence that, even for those like our respondents who manage to get into formal waged work, incorporation plays out differentially. For, cisheteropatriarchal racial capitalism, even in its equity and diversity iteration, remains an oppressive difference machine. It is apparent in these narratives that inclusion cannot overcome the structural good jobs/bad jobs dichotomy of late capitalism.

⁴ See Mills and Oswin (2024) for a detailed discussion of our respondents’ experiences across these sectors.

2.1. Teaching (not) to transgress

David⁵ is a 38 year old cis white gay male who, at the time of our interview, had worked as a full time elementary school teacher in Windsor for fifteen years. He loves his job. It can be stressful, but he thoroughly enjoys working with students and has great relationships with colleagues. David is securely employed and well paid, and he describes the quality of life in Windsor for him, his husband and children as ‘amazing’, particularly given easy access to nature and a low cost of living.

When David began training to become a teacher, he did not anticipate that he would be able to build such a life for himself in his home town. He states:

I thought I was going to have to move to Toronto. I didn’t think I was going to be able to live in Windsor and be gay so I used to research schools in Toronto...my perception was that I couldn’t be an openly gay man in Windsor and be a teacher which turned out not to be true. But also 15 years ago I don’t think we had the equity piece in our schools right? like it wasn’t at the forefront. Now – my school board – I’m very proud of it. It’s very active in supporting diversity for all

At the same time, David realistically acknowledges that homophobia looms. In answer to an interview question about whether he experiences any stress at work related to his sexuality, he replies:

Not stress but...I worry that the potential is there, right?...Being disliked, you know I’ve not experienced it for being gay at work but I know it will eventually happen, that I’ll hear parents say it. I’m dreading that time.

If these fears are ever borne out, David has a union that, he says, takes equity and diversity, including LGBTQ+ issues, very seriously. He also feels secure knowing that provincial and federal anti-discrimination laws are in place and on his side; and he says he is in very good standing with colleagues and his principal because he is professional, reliable, and a hard worker. As a valuable member of the team at his school, David is also optimistic about his future. He says that not only does he feel protected as a queer person, but that his identity opens up doors for him:

[N]ot just being gay but being a male, I get opportunities. Like, if there’s a conference and they have to pick... like I’m going because 39 women put their names in and one man... And if it’s something to do with LGBT – you know my principal called me into the office and asked me to pick out books for the library that reflected LGBT lives. He said, ‘I need an insider’s opinion’. So, I get opportunities.

Further, David has plans to move up, to perhaps become a principal or to work for the school board as a consultant. He said there are no out gay principals or school board consultants and that becoming one himself would be an important act of representation, and that he would use any administrative power to open up opportunities for other queer people. For, he noted, not all queer people have his privilege as a gender conforming and healthy person. He specifically brought up the examples of trans people and HIV+ gay men, saying that he knows that the world can still be ‘small-minded’ in relation to these and other LGBTQ+ subjects and he wants to help combat that sort of discrimination.

Kai is also a teacher. A 25 year old white queer trans man, he has a dog and a big community of friends and is generally happy in Sudbury, though he may eventually try living somewhere else “just for the life experience.” Kai, like David, went to teacher’s college and is board certified. But he works as an occasional teacher, a decision he made in part because he also works in the non-profit sector, for a trans service organization. He likes having a foot in both worlds – getting to work

⁵ All respondent names are pseudonyms. All listed sexual orientation and gender identities are respondents’ self-descriptions.

with school kids, and supporting trans people. Kai says that he deals with misgendering sometimes but that most colleagues treat him respectfully, even if some are a bit awkward. In this regard, he says he feels the effects of equity policies within schools. He is also grateful that has non-discrimination laws and a supportive union to rely on if necessary.

Kai finds his teaching work hard, though, for a couple reasons. One relates to what he describes as the superficiality of the school board's diversity and equity approach:

they're very comfortable with putting me as, for example, a spokesperson for there or I would say a token trans person to represent their school board. They're very comfortable with that. They like that there is diversity within their school populations that they can boast about.

But if Kai tries to advocate for trans youth through his work, he experiences disinterest or even hostility. He gives an example of a presentation he was asked to put together for the school board on the meaning of the rainbow flag. Kai focused in his presentation on how the flag relates to ongoing struggles for trans youth today, and talked about how trans youth can advocate for themselves by forming Gay Straight Alliances in schools (which is a legally protected right in Ontario). The board refused to use the presentation, though. Kai says:

They wanted me to talk more about like the history of the rainbow flag and why it's important and how us raising the rainbow flag makes our school board very inclusive. But they didn't want to do the work to actually be inclusive. They just wanted the flag. So I was like, thanks. Thank you for wasting my time. So I did all this work to make this presentation. And then they were like, 'too much.'

Kai also finds teaching work difficult because although occasional teachers are an obvious necessity within school systems, he does not experience "a lot of respect for that position." Kai recounted various examples when schools at which he worked did not respect legally protected break times, his mental health needs, and generally treated him, "as a robot rather than a human being."

Regarding the work at the trans non-profit, Kai said that it is tough on him to do both jobs, because the non-profit work barely pays and he ends up working 50 to 60 h weeks to make ends meet. But he persists because he finds it to be better work. Quoting Kai again:

[There is a] difference between working in a queer affirming space compared to, you know, even spaces that aren't necessarily like discriminatory but just aren't actively seeking out or supporting queer and trans folks... This is a very harm reductive space... [I]'s very, very different than when you're in a space that's like more capitalist centered or in a space that doesn't acknowledge the intersections of what it's like to be queer and trans in society. And I didn't realize that I was missing that, you know, until I had the opportunity to work here and understand that, like, you can be in a space that acknowledges your identity and doesn't just tolerate it, because being queer or trans or both in like a work community really does affect the way that you interact with people, your mental health, your ability to perform your job on a daily basis.

2.2. Support in the service sector

The importance of a workplace that does more than 'just tolerate' one's queer- or *trans*-ness was stressed by many interviewees, including Jade, a 26 year old white bisexual trans woman working for a retail chain in Windsor. Her employer is an international company that, she says, takes diversity very seriously:

When I started there it was one of the first things the manager said was just how proactive they were and how positive they were towards the LGBT community.

Starting there, I actually wound up learning that lots of co-workers were actually in the community one way or another.

Jade loves her job because everyone is 'so supportive.' She has built close friendships with co-workers (to whom she came out before even telling her family), and her manager is excited about her transition and has helped her build confidence about it. Indeed, Jade actually prefers the days that she works to her days off.

Having gone straight into the workforce after graduating from high school, Jade has worked many jobs, including some that were difficult and uncomfortable. Most of her previous work was in food service and while co-workers were generally friendly and supportive, customers were another matter,⁶ and she found the work itself challenging. Jade deals with anxiety and also has what she describes as a 'fine motor skills problem.' She says: "I had trouble trying to meet the pace very well and the stress of trying to do so would kind eat away at my confidence a bit." At one fast food restaurant job, she had a good manager who understood her need to work at a slightly slower pace. But when management changed, even though the new boss was positive towards her, she found that her co-workers became critical of her. Jade says that her co-workers were, "trying to make sure they kept their jobs, even if it meant, I don't know, cutting down the lower, the weaklings, I guess."

At the retail job she loves, Jade is supported not just as a bisexual trans person. Her health needs are addressed. She works in the back of store processing merchandise, she can work at her own pace, and her manager allows her to schedule shifts around her therapy and medical appointments. She was concerned at the time of our interview, though, that she had recently been having trouble getting shifts. Her company had just merged with another and become "one big mega store" and "because of that we've had a large increase in how much staff there is." And, with the merger, the timing of shifts had changed to start earlier. But Jade lives across town from the store and no bus runs early enough to get her there in time for the new shift start time. Making ends meet is thus a concern for her. She plans to go back to school to take software engineering courses, but worries she might not be able to find an employer in that field that is as supportive as her current one, and she needs to hold on to her benefits for health reasons.

Another respondent working in the service sector is Lee, a 22 year old Indigenous bisexual cis woman. At the time of our interview, she was back in Sudbury from studying for her undergraduate degree abroad, and working for the summer at two jobs – one at a chain restaurant and the other at a neighbourhood bar. She receives financial support from her family for her studies, but her expenses are considerable and she works as many hours as possible to try to avoid accumulating student debt. Lee plans to eventually pursue graduate work and possibly return to Sudbury to work as an organizer in the non-profit sector. She looks forward to being able to work in that realm because: "everyone's an individualist in part time work, everyone. They're like, 'I'm gonna come here and see what I can get from this work,' whereas the non-profit work is very different. Everyone's thinking, 'what can I give to this kind of work?'" And while she grew up thinking that she needed and wanted to leave Sudbury due to its blue collar orientation (Lee was raised in the knowledge that boys went into trades and girls became nurses or teachers, which would not have suited her), she finds that the city's economy has changed in ways that give her more options.

In regards to the restaurant and bar work, Lee says it is fine. Not as monotonous and grueling as work she did previously for a big box retailer, and she has good, professional and sometimes even friendly relationships with bosses and co-workers. She works front of house at both the restaurant and the bar and says she deals with plenty of casual

⁶ For a full analysis of the relationship between customer abuse and aggression and our respondents' workplace experiences, see Mills and Owens (2023).

sexism and homo-phobia/ bi-phobia, but nothing that she cannot handle. The kitchen staff at the restaurant are all white cis men, she says, and they act as if it is a 'locker room.' And customers at the bar are a diverse bunch, to whom she comes out selectively and cautiously. As Lee observed that the economy of the city has changed, she also says the culture has changed. The day of our interview, she said that that morning she had heard the hosts of a mainstream local radio show say, 'Happy Pride!', and remarked that: "right now for the most part in Sudbury, hegemonic culture is that it's not cool to be a bigot. It just isn't. And most people won't stand for outright bigotry. There's still things they [Sudbury inhabitants] say that are offensive but they tend to be more casual bigotry." Lee continued:

There is violence, especially verbal violence towards queer people in Sudbury but, in terms of my identities, it's more dangerous to be outwardly First Nations and to dare to be culturally Indigenous in Sudbury... There is a lot more risk to being First Nations than there is to being queer right now as how I perceive it.

After a pause, she then concluded this thought, with, "that's not to say about trans people everywhere."

Asserting that, "I get way more flack for being Indigenous than I do for being queer," Lee finds that there are more allies in the workplace and in the city at large for queers than for Indigenous people. She says that when she recounts stories of customers saying homophobic things to bosses or co-workers, "they really have my back and they're like 'oh my god I can't believe they said that.'" But when she relays a story about experiencing anti-Indigeneity, "it's a much more subdued reaction. They're like, 'oh I can't believe he said that, like what the heck he said that?'" But it's like by no means as big, there much more laughing about it."

2.3. Blue collar desires and defaults

Sam, a 26 year old Indigenous heterosexual trans man living in Sudbury, aspires to work in the mining sector and has laid good ground work for such a career path. In high school, Sam demonstrated an aptitude for sciences. Once he got to university, while his connections with the LGBTQ+ student group on campus set him on a path to both coming out as trans and creating a strong network of community connections, he decided that an academic route was not for him and transferred to a local college. He chose to pursue accreditation as a millwright as it is "definitely, out of the trades, one of the most broad, so you do a little bit of welding, you do some piping... it's definitely like just a mechanic of a lot of different things." While there are opportunities in his field in Sudbury, he is hesitant to apply anywhere, though. Sam says:

I want to wait to get top surgery... I'm scared to be in a more male dominated industry... cause like showering would be difficult if I work in like a dirty environment where people just shower all together right? That's not something that's necessarily inclusive or that I feel comfortable doing... I'm a lot more conscious about, like where I can work that I would feel comfortable, safe, and not potentially outed just based on being with a bunch of guys.

While he waits for the right time to enter the field in which he is trained, Sam works at a call centre. He says he got lucky in that job because there was another trans employee who "pretty much paved the way" for him. As his co-worker had already worked with management and human resources and made sure that their employer followed legal guidelines, when Sam came out, "there was no questioning... no issues." In terms of colleagues, one person refused to use Sam's pronouns, but he 'was talked to' and then left Sam alone. Other co-workers, in what Sam describes as a very LGBTQ+ friendly workplace with many LGBTQ+ employees, were extremely supportive and he says that he does not experience transphobia or, indeed, anti-Indigeneity, at work. In addition to reporting experiencing no stress related to his identity at work, Sam says his employer facilitated his transition by, for instance, giving him

time off for medical appointments and ensuring he is comfortable with workplace bathrooms. Further, he gets full time hours and benefits. He does not particularly like the work, though, finding it insufficiently challenging and at times degrading due to customer abuse, and he wants to use his skills. So he looks forward to moving on when the time is right and hopes to be able to eventually blend in within the mining sector.

Jeff, a 26 year old cis white gay man, is likewise doing work that he did not explicitly choose. He studied and has a passion for music, but works on the assembly line at one of Windsor's automotive manufacturing plants, a job that he feels fortunate to have gotten through personal connections. Jeff says the work is good – predictable, full time, with benefits which cover things like therapy and anxiety medication, and well enough remunerated that he can save up to eventually get his own place in Windsor or maybe even move to Toronto or Montreal where he might have more opportunity to work in his chosen field. And as there is much opportunity to talk to people while working on the line, he has made many friends at work. Jeff says he does not make a point of talking about his sexuality at the plant. Some of his older co-workers: "have said homophobic and racist things in the past. It's just kind of general bigotry that I just don't want to inflame and cause issues." But he is "more connected with people around my age... I guess I find myself, for the most part, more comfortable like revealing that about myself to them... It's not even a real formal coming out... I mean sometimes I'll just drop it casually."

While Jeff is out in an under the radar way at work, he feels isolated there as a queer person and talks about wanting to eventually participate in his union's LGBTQ+ diversity initiatives. He has a queer social circle outside of work, filled mostly with people he has met online and some of whom he visits in other cities in his spare time. But he has seen flyers from the union about its diversity initiatives and is heartened by their existence. Overall, though, Jeff does not feel that blue collar work impacts LGBTQ+ people especially negatively. Rather, he states:

I think for a lot of people it's not... we have a common enemy and it's the... very wealthy people who are cutting back on our services, or the people who are sending our jobs overseas. I think there are bigger issues then, you know, who somebody loves and I get that impression from a lot of the people that I grew up around and talk to. Where it's like, I don't care if the guy that I work with has a boyfriend or a girlfriend. But I do care if he decides to try to dismantle our union.

3. Conclusion

Based on decades of scholarship, we now have plenty of evidence that heteronormativity, cisnormativity, homophobia and transphobia persist in labour markets and workplaces even in locales where legal protections for queer and trans people exist. Otherwise put by another one of our respondents (a 65 year old cis bisexual woman in Sudbury whose public pension after a lifetime of work is so woefully insufficient that she must cobble together several part-time jobs to get by), there is a sense that, "we've come far... but we've still got miles to go." And a conventional wisdom has emerged within mainstream LGBTQ+ organizing as well as within academic fields like administrative and organizational studies, social work and psychology – the fields in which most research on LGBTQ+ workplace experiences and labour market outcomes is carried out – that we can best meet this reality with more and better legislation and equity-based training. What we need, we are told repeatedly in the scholarly literature and by organizations like Egale, is to stay the course of laying down 'social infrastructure' in order to achieve 'cultural and societal shifts' toward LGBTQ+ equality. Decades of queer and trans Marxist and materialist scholarship orients us differently, however. This body of work attests that we simply cannot expect inclusion into exploitative and unjust systems to produce anything other than more, if reorganized, exploitation and injustice and it thus pushes us to move away from unbridled faith in inclusionary mechanisms and toward structural skepticism.

Moreover, this research was conducted in 2018–2019, when the mainstream perception was that the project of liberal inclusion for queer and trans people in Canada – like the projects of multicultural inclusion of immigrants and reconciliation with Indigenous peoples – was firmly steering us in the direction of more and better progress. In 2025, however, the inaccuracy of that perception is clearly apparent. The fissures identified in the homonormativity and homonationalism literatures have widened under resurgent right wing assault – especially on trans people and the rights of queer and trans youth to self-determination – just as immigrant scapegoating (in the face of huge rises in temporary migration, enabled by the federal government at the behest of employers and the higher education sector) and anti-Indigenous racism (such as residential school denialism) have also flourished. The liberal politics of inclusion have indeed benefited LGBTQ+ workers, but have also increased polarization *within* that group, much as Linda McDowell’s research in the early 2000s showed growing differences among women in the UK’s new service economy under neoliberalism. When Lisa Duggan argued homonormativity is the sexual politics of neoliberalism, she was arguing that the economic and trade policy prescriptions associated with neoliberalism have social and cultural corollary, which mirrors and reinforces the individualism and privatization of those prescriptions. Focused on “a privatized, depoliticized gay culture anchored in domesticity and consumption” (2001, p. 179) and on the right to marriage and military service as modalities of gay normative and institutional inclusion, the new homonormativity reinforces market discipline, dependency on low wage jobs, and family discipline. In doing so it has functioned as a political discourse and movement that co-produces successful, responsible white gay liberal subjects alongside queered others – racialized and gendered precarious workers, “illegal” migrants, single parents, unhoused people, the working and jobless poor. The new homonormativity has provided a veneer of inclusion for deeply polarizing economic and social policies, including the privatization of social welfare services, and the financialization and assetization of housing – and the expansion of precarious employment relations.

The massive bodies of scholarship on LGBTQ+ workplace and labour market inclusion that have been built up in relatively short order are important and impressive. The academy is straight and cis and it matters that LGBTQ+ issues at work get studied. But, study after study after study shows the same thing – that the benefits of labour market and workplace inclusion are experienced in limited and uneven ways by queer and trans people. And study after study after study offer discrimination and prejudice as sole explanatory factors; never mentioning capitalism as a structuring condition although queer and trans people in many places, like most people in many places, live with low wages, hard to come by benefits, damaging demands for ‘fitness’ and ‘productivity’, housing scarcity, and broken health, education and transit systems. In this paper, we thus join the chorus to deliberately sing off key within it, and ideally attune it to a parallel song. Decades of legislative gains and employment equity policies and practices within cisheteropatriarchal racial capitalist Canada have, in essence, filtered our respondents into the various ‘good jobs’ and ‘bad jobs’ of these two particular neoliberal urban economies. So, while homonormativity “anesthetizes queer communities [including queer scholarly communities] into passively accepting alternative forms of inequality” (Manalansan, 2005, p. 142), we argue, with Petrus Liu, that, “the specter of the material... is an enabling kind of haunting that keeps us on our toes” (2020, p. 31). ‘Queer’ and ‘trans’ operate in opposition to the normative, and capitalism is a norm that needs to be opposed by more queer and trans scholars and organizers. As Lisa Duggan noted when she recognized the force of homonormativity more than twenty years ago, “only an interconnected, analytically diverse, cross-fertilizing and expansive left can seize this moment to lead us elsewhere” (2003, p. xxii).

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Natalie Oswin: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.
Suzanne Mills: Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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The data that has been used is confidential.

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